
Biodiversity and its Conservation in India: A Review

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Abstract:

Biodiversity refers to the number and variety of living organisms along with ecological facilities in which they exist. Biodiversity has several values, such as economical, ecological, medicinal, ethical, aesthetical, and social, etc. India is one of the 34 mega biodiversity hotspots of the world. (Agarwal et al, 2018) Over the years, biodiversity has been facing rapid depletion as a result of excessive exploitation of resources, habitat loss, poaching of animals, climatic changes, pollution, diseases, etc. To correct this scenario, vital steps for the conservation of biodiversity have to be taken by the public along with the government, semi-government, and social organizations. Thus, biodiversity conservation has become a major issue in the present time in the world. Conservation of biodiversity is being done by taking some strict steps, forming various legislations, the establishing protected areas, zoos, botanical gardens, seed banks etc. In this paper, the overview of biodiversity and its types, the status of biodiversity in India, major threats to biodiversity, conservation strategies, and various steps to be taken for the conservation of biodiversity have been discussed.

Keywords: Biodiversity, Conservation, Habitat, Ecological, Social, etc.

Introduction:

Biodiversity is important for all living organisms including human being. Because all living beings are inter linked directly or indirectly to one another. They indirectly effect the life of another organism. Biodiversity is a **variety of species** on earth, **included** different microorganisms, plants, and animals, including terrestrial or marine and other aquatic ecosystems. W. G. Rosen may have been the first to use the term biodiversity in 1985. Biodiversity (1992) has been defined as the variability among living organisms from all sources, including inter alia, terrestrial, marine, and other aquatic ecosystems and the ecological complexes of which they are a part. The survival of life on Earth and the health of ecosystems depends on biodiversity. It helps to maintain the natural balance and provides vital services that humans depend on, including food, medicine, water, and climate

regulation. The loss of biodiversity threatens all of these, making its conservation critical for the future of humanity and the earth.

Biodiversity can be discussed at three levels:

Genetic Diversity: The fundamental components of all living organisms are genes. It is basic units of hereditary information transmitted from one generation to another. The diversity of genes within a species is referred to as genetic biodiversity. For a species to have a healthy reproducing population, this genetic variety is necessary

Species Diversity: This refers to the variation within species. It relates to the number of species in a defined area. The diversity of species can be measured by the variety of plants, animals, algae, microorganisms, fungi, etc., found within a particular geographical area. There are more species in certain places than others. Areas

rich in species diversity are called hotspots of diversity

Ecosystem Diversity: Ecosystem diversity includes all the species and their interaction with abiotic factors. It shows tremendous diversity due to variation in altitude, temperature, humidity, etc. For example, India has a more diverse ecology with its deserts, rain forests, mangroves, coral reefs, wetlands, estuaries, and alpine meadows. There is a latitudinal gradient in species diversity.

Status of Biodiversity in India:

India is one of the most biodiverse countries out of 17 identified mega diverse countries. India has covered only 2.4% of the world's land area and accommodates 7-8% of species of flora and fauna, including more than 45,000 species of plants and 91,000 species of animals. It is located where the Indo-Malayan, Palearctic, and Afro-tropical regions converge, supporting a wealth of biodiversity. India has four of the 34 biodiversity hotspots that have been recognized worldwide: the Himalaya, Indo-Burma, the Western Ghats, and Sunda land. With hundreds of different types of crop plants, including rice, maize, millets, and others, India is also known as a center for agricultural diversity. The diverse physical features and climatic conditions of India are responsible for a variety of ecosystems, such as forests, grasslands, wetlands, desert, coastal and marine ecosystems. (Source: India's Fifth National Report to The Convention on Biological Diversity, MoEF, GOI).

Threats to Biodiversity:

There are many threats to biodiversity, like human population, habitat loss and fragmentation, poaching of wildlife, over exploitation, climate change, etc. But the main threat to biodiversity is natural habitat loss & destruction.

Human Population: The world's population would be increasing day by day.

So, increased demand for food, places for shelter, timber, clothes, wood fuels, etc. also increases. This exerts pressure on limited natural resources, land, forest regions, vegetation, etc. This causes an impact on natural resources, forest cover, the environment, vegetation, and biodiversity. Humans are clearing the natural habitat of other organisms for agriculture, developing cities, industries, etc., to fulfill the demand of the increasing population

Habitat loss & fragmentation: Habitat loss is the most important cause of loss of biodiversity. Deforestation and grassland clearing have been done for agriculture and shelter place purposes. It caused destruction of the natural habitat of flora and fauna.

Poaching: Poaching is the killing or hunting of wildlife for pleasure and for the formation of products from their parts like elephant teeth, rhino horn, nails of tiger, lion, etc. There is a ban on the trade of these products nationally and internationally, but smuggling of these wildlife or products from them takes place. Wildlife such as species of snakes, tigers, turtles, some species of birds, etc. are killed for their skin and feather and other purpose. Over hunting of wildlife decreases the number of wildlife species. India makes strict legislation to protect wildlife from this illegal trade and hunting. But people's awareness is also important to protect wildlife and refuse the buying of products made from wildlife parts.

Over exploitation: Human beings have always depended on nature for fundamental needs like food, shelter, and cloth, but when these 'needs' turn to 'greed', it leads to overexploitation of natural resources.

Climate change: The changing climate patterns have profound effects on ecosystems and species around the world. Climate change and the increase in temperature affect other environmental factors such as rainfall regimes, sea level, and precipitation that cause land degradation, pollution, invasive species, and

overexploitation. Various man-made activities led to habitat destruction, which affects the distribution of species in terrestrial as well as aquatic ecosystems.

Invasion of exotic species: When exotic species are introduced unintentionally for whatever purpose, some of them turn invasive, competing with native species for food and other nutrients, and causing a decline of indigenous species and reducing biodiversity.

Biodiversity conservation:

Biodiversity provides food, fruits, medicine, and other ecological services. Conserving biodiversity can maintain food webs and food chains and also help to maintain the balance of climate and environment. Thus, conservation of biodiversity is most important for ecosystems. Biodiversity conservation is the protection and active management of biodiversity to ensure the survival of maximum species diversity, habitat, ecosystem, genetic diversity to obtain resources for sustainable development (Dharkar *et al*, 2021). When we protect and conserve the entire ecosystem, its biodiversity at all levels is protected. To save the tiger, we save the entire forest. This approach is called in-situ (on-site) conservation. However, ex-situ (off-site) conservation is the preferred method in cases where an animal or plant is endangered or threatened and requires immediate action to prevent extinction.

In situ conservation:

(i)Protection of habitat:

In India, biodiversity-rich regions and ecologically unique areas are legally protected as biosphere reserves, national parks and sanctuaries, heritage sites, etc. India now has 18 biosphere reserves, 106 national parks, 574 wildlife sanctuaries, 44 heritage sites, 57 tiger reserves, and 33 elephant reserves. Additionally, India's religious and cultural traditions have always placed a strong emphasis on preserving nature. In situ conservation mainly controls the Ministry of Environment and Forests, Govt. of India. It is cost-effective to conserve plants as well as animal species simultaneously.

- **National parks and sanctuaries:** It is prohibited area for killing, hunting, shooting, or capture wildlife in national parks and sanctuaries, this are protected places devoted to the conservation of wildlife and its ecosystem. With their vast biodiversity, India's national parks and wildlife sanctuaries stretch from the southern point of Tamil Nadu to the Himalayan area. Due to the presence of rare species, wildlife reserves in India attract tourists from all over the world. India's natural heritage is popular for its diversity and breadth, with 106 national parks and more than 574 wildlife sanctuaries.
- **Biosphere Reserves:** The biosphere reserves conserve some representative ecosystems as a whole for long-term in situ conservation. In India, there are now 18 biosphere reserves.

List of Biosphere Reserves in India

Sr. No.	Name	Location (State)	Sr. No.	Name	Location (State)
1	Nilgiri	Tamil Nadu, Kerala and Karnataka	10	Dehang-Dibang	Arunachal Pradesh.
2	Nanda Devi	Uttarakhand	11	Pachmarhi	Madhya Pradesh.
3	Nokrek	Meghalaya	12	Khangchendzonga	Sikkim.
4	Great Nicobar	Andaman And Nicobar Islands	13	Agasthyamalai	Kerala.
5	Gulf of Mannar	Tamil Nadu	14	Achanakamar - Amarkantak	Madhya Pradesh and Chhattishgarh
6	Manas	Assam	15	Kachchh	Gujarat State
7	Sunderbans	West Bengal	16	Cold Desert	Himachal Pradesh
8	Simlipal	Orissa	17	Seshachalam Hills	Andhra Pradesh
9	Dibru-Saikhowa	Assam	18	Panna	Madhya Pradesh

Ex situ Conservation:

- **Botanical Gardens:** It is a side where plants are conserved, consisting of botanical gardens, medicinal plant parks, etc. In India, there are now 122 botanical gardens. The Acharya Jagadish Chandra Bose Indian Botanic Garden in Howrah, West Bengal is oldest and largest botanical garden in India. It spread on about a 273-acre area.
- **Zoos:** A zoo is a place where people can see and interact with animals, usually for conservation, education, and research reasons. The India, has. The main objectives of zoos, which usually hold a range of animals from around the world, are to promote animal conservation, give visitors educational experiences, and carry out scientific study on animal behaviour, biology, and reproduction. In addition, a lot of contemporary zoos work to replicate the natural environments of its animals and run initiatives to save endangered species.
- **Gene Bank:** Gene banks are facilities where genetic material can be artificially preserved at low temperature and made accessible to breeders, researchers.
- **Seed Banks:** A seed bank is a collection of dried seeds that are kept at a low temperature for preservation.

Conclusions:

India is one of the most biodiverse countries with 7-8% species diversity in the world. Regions with more species are more stable. Conservation of biodiversity included protection and efficient use of natural resources for the future. Awareness among local communities and peoples are valuable for biodiversity conservation. It is also important to strictly implement of laws related to environment protection is important. Tougher the punishment for killing and smuggling of wildlife. Strengthening governmental and non-governmental organizations working on biodiversity conservation, so that they can effectively carry out their work.

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